

THE COLLECTION IDENTIFICATION AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DIFFERENT ISOLATES OF *Ganoderma lucidum* IN MARATHWADA REGION.

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Abstract

Background: The most extensively used mushroom in medicine history is *Ganoderma*, which is also widely distributed.

Methods: A total of 10 *Ganoderma lucidum* samples were gathered from different parts of the Parbhani district's VNMKV campus. These samples were identified as *G. lucidum* based on microscopic inspection, sporocarp and growth on media, and basidiospore characteristics. Using the standard species description, the collected fruiting bodies were identified based on their morphological and microscopic features.

Results: Fruiting bodies were often big, stipitate, dimidiate, and occasionally suborbicular. Their upper and lateral surfaces were covered in hard, shiny substances, and the color of the basidiospores was brown. They were oval-shaped, thick-walled, and had a rounded base.

Conclusion: All of the isolates were assigned the GL-1, GL-2, GL-3, GL-4, GL-5, and GL-6 designations based on the morphology of the basidiocarp and basidiospore.

Key words – mushroom, medicine history, *Ganoderma*,

Introduction

A macrofungus called *Ganoderma* is frequently seen on decomposing wood. The majority of *Ganoderma* species are pathogenic, meaning they can cause a variety of diseases in plants, including stem and white rot. *Ganoderma* may comprise over 2000 species (Adaskaveg and Gilbertson, 1986). *Ganoderma* comes from the Greek word "gános," which means brilliance and shine, and "dérma," which means skin. Since not every species in this genus has a glossy, bright surface, it does not accurately represent the physical characteristics of all species within this genus. (Bernicchia et al. 2020 and Sun et al. 2022). Though it is found all over the world, the genus *Ganoderma* is most commonly found in tropical and temperate areas, such as Africa, America, Europe, and Asia. *Ganoderma* is a plant pathogen that can kill a tree. Certain species function as saprophytes, decomposing the lignin and cellulose of their hosts to cause hardwood rot (Surendran et al., 2021). *Ganoderma* is one of many traditional remedies that have been utilized for vivacity and longevity in Asian countries for more than two millennia. It is questionable, therefore, if *Ganoderma* is a highly developed mushroom that is already available in thousands of products or a food supplement for maintaining health. Even though the market is bigger, industry issues keep it from developing a successful market (Hapuarachi et al., 2018). Mostly in China, Korea, the United States, and a few other Asian and European nations, *Ganoderma* is utilized to make a variety of cosmetic items, many of which are used for skin lightening (Jiang 2015). *Ganoderma lucidum* has demonstrated tyrosinase inhibitory action, and tyrosinase is an essential enzyme in the synthesis of melanin (Chien et al., 2008). Because of this, *Ganoderma* extracts are included in a lot of face mask cosmetics on the market, which aid in skin whitening (Hyde et al. 2010). By reducing dihydrotestosterone or prostatic levels, *Ganoderma lucidum*, together with three other herbs and zinc, stimulates hair growth in male humans (Meehan 2015). Several substrates were used in the cultivation of *Ganoderma lucidum*, and growth factors including temperature, relative humidity, water content, pH, and light intensity were monitored (Chang and Miles, 2004).

Similar cultivation took place in India at NRCM, Solan (H.P.) according to Rai (2003). *G. lucidum* grows quite well in the Marathwada region on practically all of the agricultural wastes that contain more sugar and cellulose. The majority of farmers in Marathwada cultivate edible mushrooms, and *G. lucidum* is the greatest choice because it can be cultivated on a range of agricultural wastes by controlling humidity and temperature. Mushrooms can be grown all year round by growers. Ten *Ganoderma* isolates were gathered from various locations within the Parbhani district's VNMKV campus. Based on sporocarp and growth on media,

basidiospore characteristics, and microscopic examination, the isolates were determined to be *G. lucidum*.

Material And Methods

Collection and Identification:

The VNMKV campus provided the samples. Fruits and cultural traits will be used for identification, and NMR, Solan will further validate this.

Cleaning, washing, and sterilizing: All glassware used in the experiment, including Petriplates, test tubes, conical flasks, beakers, and measuring cylinders, were thoroughly cleaned, powdered detergent washed, and then rinsed with tap water. Glassware was first dried at 600°C and then sterilized for two hours at 1800°C. Other items, such as a cork borer, blade, inoculation needle, scalpel, and scissors, were heated over a flame after being sterilized with 95% alcohol.

Results

Collection and Identification

New samples of *Ganoderma lucidum* were collected from various locations of VNMKV campus of Parbhani districts of Maharashtra during July-September for two years (2021 and 2022). Ten isolates collected from various sources have been listed in (Table 1). The prevalence of *G. lucidum* with host in natural settings was also noted during collection. It is known to grow on a variety of host plants.

Identification of *Ganoderma lucidum*

The fungus is recognized as *G. lucidum* based on microscopic examination, basidiospore characteristics, and mycelial growth on media. This culture was used for additional research, the findings of which are shown in Table 2 and Fig. 1. On PDA media, *Ganoderma lucidum* forms a thick mycelial growth. The hues vary from light yellow to white. The thin-walled, branching hyphae with clamp connections make up the aerial mycelium. Brown in color, basidiospores had thick walls, an oval form with a rounded base and truncate to narrowly rounded apex, a mildly to strongly dimpled surface, and a wall made up of many layers. The inner wall and outside wall are joined by pillars. The size of the basidiospores varied, nevertheless, ranging from 10-12 × 6.5-8.0 µm.

Morphological characters of *Ganoderma* species

Table 3 shown significant variety in macroscopic characteristics of naturally formed basidiocarp of *G. lucidum*. The variability of seven basidiomata features was investigated. The basidiocarp size, weight, and color varied significantly amongst specimens. The dry fruiting body's average weight ranged from 12.2 to 27.5 gm, while the pileus width varied from 6.5 to 18.0 cm. While the shape of the pileus varied, it might be semicircular (GL1 and GL2) or circular (GL3, GL4, GL5, GL7, GL8). The pileus surface exhibited a range of colors, including dull reddish brown, orange brown, blackish red, and dark reddish brown. However, it was also observed that the morphology

of a few isolates (GL9, GL10, and GL6) was irregular (fan-shaped).
to pileus also differed significantly. Stipe diameter and length ranged

from long and thin (more than pileus radius) to very short and thick
(less than pileus radius).

Basidiospores of *Ganodermalucidum*

Clam Connection

Mycelium

Table no. 1 Collec

Fig 1: Microscopic view of *G. lucidum*

Sample No.	Date of survey	Name of location	Latitude	Longitude	Host plant
GL-1	09/02/2021	VNMKV Campus, Near state bank of India.	19.248194	76.790123	Gulmohar
GL-2	08/03/2021	VNMKV campus, Near state bank of India.	19.249088	76.788434	Gulmohar
GL-3	09/08/2021	VNMKV campus, In front of jijau girl's hostel.	19.249158	76.787539	Gulmohar
GL-4	26/12/2021	VNMKV campus, Near food tech. college.	19.249472	76.792332	Shisar
GL-5	26/12/2021	VNMKV campus, Near vaidyanath boy's hostel.	19.249426	76.792616	Shisar
GL-6	27/07/2022	VNMKV Campus, Near state bank of India.	19.250075	76.786967	Gulmohar
GL-7	03/08/2022	VNMKV campus, Infront of Horticulture College.	19.250057	76.787002	Gulmohar
GL-8	18/08/2022	VNMKV campus, Near Seed Processing Unit.	19.254557	76.779568	Gulmohar
GL-9	18/08/2022	VNMKV campus, Near Home science college.	19.249076	76.788446	Gulmohar
GL-10	13/09/22	VNMKV campus, College of horticulture Rd.	19.248475	76.788096	Gulmohar

Table No. 2 Basidiospore morphology of *Ganoderma lucidum*

Isolate	Spore size (L×B)(µm)	Colour	Shape	Distinguishing characters
<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>	10-12× 6.5-8.0 µm	Brown	Ovate	Rounded base and truncate, non-vacuolated, dimpled with wall composed of several layers.

Discussion

A significant portion of *G. lucidum* specimens were gathered from Gulmohar trees, while a smaller number of fruiting bodies were discovered to be connected to Arjun trees in the wild during the summer and fall, when temperatures ranged from 25 to 300 degrees Celsius. The typical host plants for *G. lucidum* are hard woods. Additionally, it can grow on logs in a saprophytic or parasitic manner (Singh et al., 2007; Seo and Kirk, 2000). The fruiting bodies are often big, stipitate, dimidiate, and reddish brown in color. They are also coated on the upper and lateral surfaces with a hard, shiny substance that resembles sealing wax. Pileus, rough-textured, reddish-brown, 2.0–5.0 cm broad. Stripe length: 1.5–4.5 cm; thickness: 0.5–2.0 cm. The surface of the pileus often appeared varnished. (Furtado 1965) reported that the varnished appearance of the basidiocarp of many polypores was due to an amorphous substance secreted by the hyphae and the characteristic shiny cover is seen particularly in isolates of *G. lucidum*. On the basis of mycelial growth on media, characteristics of basidiospore and microscopic observation the fungus is identified as *G. lucidum*. Similar type of result was recorded by several workers. Kapoor (2014) and Rawat (2018) studied the basidiospore morphology of *G. lucidum* and found basidiospore were ovate, with a rounded base and truncate to narrowly rounded apex, double walled and size in the range of 6.5 – 8.0 µm × 10.0 -12.0 µm. According to Saunsia and John (2020) basidiospore were double walled ellipsoid, brown in colour and the size varied from 8.7 × 5.3 to 10.7 × 7.1 µm. Macroscopic characteristics of the basidiocarp of *G. lucidum* that were spontaneously formed showed a significant degree of variety. Environmental factors have a significant impact on the variety in basidiocarp shape of *G. lucidum*, according to Ryavarden (1994). Seo and Kirk (2000) and Sun et al. (2022) have suggested that pileus characters (color, size, surface, and thickness) and stipe characters (attachment to pileus, relative thickness, and length) are helpful for species identification. Similar findings about the shape of the basidiocarp and basidiospore in the wild fruit body of *G. lucidum* have been published by Xing (2019), Adaskaveg and Gilbertson (1986), Furtado (1962), and Seo et al. (1995).

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Table No. 3 Morphological characters of *Ganoderma spp.*

Sample No.	Average. Wt. of fruiting body (g)	Pileus colour	Pileus shape	Pileus diameter (cm)	Stipe length (cm)	Stipe diameter (cm)	Texture of fruiting body
GL-1	20.2	Dark reddish brown	Semicircular	15.00	4.7	7.5	Hard woody
GL-2	15.5	Reddish brown	Semicircular	6.5	9.5	6.2	Hard woody
GL-3	16.0	Light orange brown	Circular	11.5	7.0	8.0	Hard woody
GL-4	12.5	Blackish red	Circular	12.0	6.0	6.0	Hard woody
GL-5	14.9	Dull orange with white margin	Circular	12.5	5.5	7.5	Spongy
GL-6	18.2	Drak reddish brown	Fan shaped	12.6	7.7	7.5	Hard woody
GL-7	12.2	Light orange with white margin	Circular	10.5	3.4	2.5	Spongy
GL-8	20.2	Dark brown	Circular	17.5	7.0	7.5	Hard woody
GL-9	22.0	Dull reddish with white margin	Irregular	18.0	5.5	9.0	Hard woody
GL-10	27.5	Dark brown with white margin	Irregular	17.0	7.5	10	Hard woody